

Bridging Eastern and Western Financial Markets

Ivan Mok^a

^a *Serial Entrepreneur // Fintech, Crypto & Blockchain // Strategic Planner // Business Advisor, Hong Kong*

Abstract

1. Introduction

Ivan Mok Founder of IKF Crypto Solutions Limited Ivan was a serial entrepreneur specialized in Fintech and Financial Architect for more than 8 years. He has founded companies within south-east Asia ranging from mobile payment, mortgage fund, diamond finance, private equity and offshore fund. He acted as ICO advisor and business consultant for blockchain projects in Asia in recent years.

Author biography

Ivan Mok Ivan Mok Founder of IKF Crypto Solutions Limited Ivan was a serial entrepreneur

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